

TECHNISCHE
UNIVERSITÄT
WIEN

Data management plan (DMP)

WatermakNN: Evaluating Black-Box Watermarking Robustness in Deep Learning

WNNEBB

Version	Effective date	Description of document/changes
1.0	30/11/2025	First version of the DMP – created for the start of the project

Level of distribution		This DMP is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0) . It is publicly available under 10.5281/zenodo.17650613 .
-----------------------	---	---

Project details

Project Coordinator Principal Investigator	Stefan Hamm, e12346011@student.tuwien.ac.at, TU Wien, ROR: ror.org/04d836q62 https://orcid.org/0009-0008-9108-5180
Contact person (responsible for data management and DMP)	Stefan Hamm, e12346011@student.tuwien.ac.at, TU Wien, ROR: ror.org/04d836q62 https://orcid.org/0009-0008-9108-5180
Contributors	Stefan Hamm, e12346011@student.tuwien.ac.at, TU Wien, ROR: ror.org/04d836q62, Data Manager Vinzent Beer, vinzent.beer@student.tuwien.ac.at, TU Wien, ROR: ror.org/04d836q62, Project Member
Start date	2025-11-30
End date	2026-07-26
Funder	-
Funding programme, grant number	-
Internal project number	-

List of acronyms

DMP	data management plan
RDM	research data management
...	...
...	...
...	...
...	...
...	...
...	...

Content

INTRODUCTION	4
Science Europe practical guide, FAIR data	4
Relevant Policies and Guidelines	4
1. DATA DESCRIPTION	5
1a Lists of datasets that will be reused or produced	5
1b Data generation and reuse	6
2. DOCUMENTATION AND DATA QUALITY	6
2a Data organisation, metadata and documentation	6
2b Data quality control	6
3. STORAGE AND BACKUP DURING RESEARCH PROCESS	7
3a Storage and backup facilities	7
3b Data security and protection of sensitive data	7
4. LEGAL AND ETHICAL REQUIREMENTS	8
4a Personal data	8
4b Intellectual property rights and ownership	8
4c Ethical issues	8
5. DATA SHARING AND LONG-TERM PRESERVATION	8
5a Data publication and access conditions	8
5b Long-term preservation and deletion of data	9
6. RDM RESPONSIBILITIES AND RESOURCES	9
6a RDM-roles and responsibilities	9
6b Resources	10

Introduction

Science Europe practical guide, FAIR data

A DMP is a structured document that keeps record of what research data is created and what happens to that data during and after a project. It helps with planning the research process and defining responsibilities in a research project involving several researchers or institutions.

For writing this DMP, we followed [the recommendations of Science Europe](#) as they reflect the guidelines agreed upon by the major funders in Europe.

To make our data FAIR, they generally will be treated according to the following criteria:

- We will make our data findable, by uploading it to a data repository that provides a persistent identifier and adding relevant metadata.
- We will make our data accessible by providing open access to data, wherever possible. In cases, where open access is not possible, we will provide meaningful metadata plus contact information for access requests.
- We will make our data interoperable by providing and describing data in a way that is common within our domain by using the same file formats, schemas and vocabularies. We will provide good documentation for all our datasets.
- We will make our data reusable by adding metadata and comprehensive Readme files to all published datasets. The descriptions include details on the methodology used, analytical and procedural information. In case of publication, licenses for code and data will always be assigned and clearly marked.

Relevant Policies and Guidelines

- European Commission's document on Ethics and Data Protection:
https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/ethics-and-data-protection_he_en.pdf
- Code of conduct
<https://www.tuwien.at/index.php?eID=dms&s=4&path=Richtlinien%20und%20Verordnungen/Code%20of%20Conduct%20fuer%20wissenschaftliches%20Arbeiten.pdf>
- Data protection
<https://www.tuwien.at/index.php?eID=dumpFile&t=f&f=209199&token=98a42a707abe5707d503069ba24f24a6ce9fee84>

1. Data description

1a Lists of datasets that will be reused or produced

Produced datasets

dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
P1	results.csv	Structured text	csv	100 - 1000 MB	no
P2	TransformedMNIST	Structured text	csv	100 - 1000 MB	no
P3	TransformedFashionMNIST	Structured text	csv	100 - 1000 MB	no
P4	SqueezenetScratchMNISTEmbedded	Configuration data	caffemodel	100 - 1000 MB	no
P5	SqueezenetScratchFashionMNISTEmbedded	Other	caffemodel	100 - 1000 MB	no

Description for "TransformedMNIST":

MNIST dataset preprocessed using standard ImageNet transformations

Description for "TransformedFashionMNIST":

Fashion MNIST dataset preprocessed using standard ImageNet transformations

Description for "SqueezenetScratchMNISTEmbedded":

Squeezenet model with trained on MNIST with embedded triggerset

Description for "SqueezenetScratchFashionMNISTEmbedded":

Model trained on Fashion MNIST with embedded trigger set

Reused datasets

dataset ID	title	source	rights (e.g. license)	contains sensitive data
R1	MNIST	https://doi.org/10.24432/C53K8Q	CC BY-SA 3.0	no

R2	Fashion MNIST	https://github.com/zalando-research/fashion-mnist	MIT	no
R3	Triggerset	https://github.com/adiyoss/WatermarkNN/tree/master/data/triggerset/pics	CC0	no

Description for "Triggerset":

Triggerset for watermark embedding

1b Data generation and reuse

Methods and software used for data generation and reuse

Reused:

- MNIST dataset 21MiB 28x28 grayscale pixel images (idx3-ubyte format)
- Fashion-MNIST dataset 36MiB 28x28 grayscale pixel images (idx3-ubyte format)
- Triggerset 16MB (jpg format)
- Squeezenet 5MB (caffemodel format)

Produced:

- Metrics for Training/Test accuracy, Attack retentions etc. 1 MB (format csv)
- Transformed MNIST and Fashion-MNIST 50MiB (format csv)
- Trained from scratch models with embedded triggerset 10MB (format caffemodel)

2. Documentation and data quality

2a Data organisation, metadata and documentation

The version control is automated in a git repository.

As there are no domain-specific metadata standards applicable, we will provide a README file at the project level, including an explanation of all values and terms used, as well as details on how the model was trained and evaluated. This will help others to identify, discover and reuse our data.

Additionally, we will provide common metadata such as title, description or keywords when publishing data in open access repositories. In such a case, we will follow the default template provided by the repository.

As far as possible, we will use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability.

To adhere to the TU Wien Code of Conduct, we maintain a structured GitHub repository with all code, configurations, and processing steps, alongside a methodology report and references to original papers. We facilitate reuse through a consistent file naming convention using the pattern

dataset_trainingtype_status (e.g., dataset_trainingtype_baseline or dataset_trainingtype_watermarked).

2b Data quality control

The following data quality checks will be done: The data will be tested for null values and outliers using automated test scripts.

3. Storage and backup during research process

3a Storage and backup facilities

For the duration of the project, storage and backup of data will be ensured by Stefan Hamm (acting as the person responsible for data management and DMP) in cooperation with the system operator.

P1 (results.csv), R1 (MNIST), R2 (Fashion MNIST), R3 (Triggerset), P2 (TransformedMNIST), P3 (TransformedFashionMNIST), P4 (SqueezenetScratchMNISTEmbedded), P5 (SqueezenetScratchFashionMNISTEmbedded) will be stored in the repository with release tags.

3b Data security and protection of sensitive data

We pay strict attention to compliance with the relevant institutional and national data protection policies listed in the introduction of this document. At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any sensitive data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.

Access to data during research:

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
P1	writing	writing	reading only
P2	writing	writing	reading only
P3	writing	writing	reading only
P4	writing	writing	reading only
P5	writing	writing	reading only
R1	writing	writing	no access
R2	writing	writing	no access
R3	writing	writing	reading only

4. Legal and ethical requirements

4a Personal data

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any personal data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.

4b Intellectual property rights and rights of use

The following individual(s) hold rights and control access to the project data: The Data Manager controls access for all datasets.

4c Ethical issues

No particular ethical issue is foreseen with the data to be used or produced by the project.

5. Data sharing and long-term preservation

5a Data publication and access conditions

As far as possible, obtained datasets will be published in repositories. Details on access conditions, reuse licenses, reasons for restrictions, etc. are collected in the table below.

dataset ID	access conditions	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
P1	Open	2025-11-30	TU Wien Research Data Repository	10.70124/9 shrg-hqn25	CC-BY-4.0
P2	Open	2025-11-30	TU Wien Research Data Repository	10.70124/9 shrg-hqn25	CC-BY-SA-4.0
P3	Open	2025-11-30	TU Wien Research Data Repository	10.70124/9 shrg-hqn25	CC-BY-SA-4.0
P4	Open	2025-11-30	TU Wien Research Data Repository	10.70124/9 shrg-hqn25	BSD-2-Clause
P5	Open	2025-11-30		10.70124/9 shrg-hqn25	BSD-2-Clause

Additionally, a snapshot of the project’s source code and the trigger set will be deposited in the TU Wien Research Data Repository together with the datasets. The final report will also be available for a detailed methodology.

Repository description:

The **TU Wien Research Data Repository** is an institutional repository that enables researchers at TU Wien to store, share, and publish their research data. It provides persistent identifiers (DOIs) for datasets, ensures long-term preservation, and supports FAIR data principles. It allows for granular access control and licensing, making it suitable for both open and restricted data.

<https://researchdata.tuwien.ac.at/> (For this project, the test instance is used:

<https://test.researchdata.tuwien.ac.at/>)

Methods or software needed to access and use data: Mostly using python with pytorch to load the model weights.

5b Long-term preservation and deletion of data

dataset ID	location for long-term storage	minimum retention period (≥ 10 years)	foreseeable research uses and/or users
P1	TU Wien Research Data Repository	10 years	Members of the scientific community, Security / adversarial-ML researcher
P2	TU Wien Research Data Repository	10 years	
P3	TU Wien Research Data Repository	10 years	
P4	TU Wien Research Data Repository	10 years	
P5	TU Wien Research Data Repository	10 years	

6. RDM responsibilities and resources

6a RDM-roles and responsibilities

The data officer Stefan Hamm will direct the data management process overall, with the research assistants responsible for ensuring metadata production, day-to-day cross-checks, back-up and other quality control activities are maintained.

6b Resources

There are no costs dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR.